

Archiving, sharing and discussing research data on Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia

Data Review

Data Citation

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Abstract

The Observatory for Political Conflict and Democracy (PoIDem) is a platform that was created by the POLCON and Years-of-Turmoil research teams (Kriesi, Hanspeter et al. 2020: 6) and covers data on protest events, election campaigns, public debates and contentious episodes (1) in 30 European countries from 2000 to 2015 (Kriesi, Hanspeter et al. 2020: 2). This data review will focus on their coverage of protest events in the dataset “poldem-protest_30”. This dataset includes the following countries covered by Discuss Data: Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania. Of the 30.000+ total entries in this dataset, there are 1.655 events listed for the before listed countries. As of summer 2024, it seems like work on the data collection has concluded. The data review contains a link leading to the official Observatory for Political Conflict and Democracy in Europe website from which both the dataset and the codebook, as well as additional information, are available as a free download.

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Data Review - Observatory for Political Conflict and Democracy in Europe

The Observatory for Political Conflict and Democracy (PolDem) is a platform that was created by the POLCON and Years-of-Turmoil research teams (Kriesi, Hanspeter et al. 2020: 6) and covers data on protest events, election campaigns, public debates and contentious episodes (1) in 30 European countries from 2000 to 2015 (Kriesi, Hanspeter et al. 2020: 2). This data review will focus on their coverage of protest events.

The unit of observation within the PolDem protest events dataset is the protest event itself. Such an event is always defined by the time it takes place, its location, and a particular protest action form. In order to gather sufficient data, a combination of both automated (Natural Language Processing [NLP]) and manual coding was employed, since such a hybrid procedure combines the strength of machine learning with the prowess of human coding (Kriesi, Hanspeter et al. 2020: 13).

Ten English-language newswire agencies – accessible via Lexis-Nexis – were drawn upon as sources. More specifically: The AFP, AP, APA, BBC, BNS, CTK, DPA, MTI, PA and PAP. Utilising these sources, the research team conducted a search for reports covering about 40 keywords using the following query string:

initiative OR referendum OR petition! OR signature! OR campaign! OR protest! OR demonstrat! OR manifest! OR marche! OR marchi! OR parade OR rall! OR picket! OR (human chain) OR riot! OR affray OR festival OR ceremony OR (street theatre) OR (road show) OR vigil OR strike! OR boycott! OR block! OR sit-in OR squat! OR mutin! OR bomb! OR firebomb! OR molotov OR graffiti OR assault OR attack OR arson OR incendiar! OR (fire I/1 raising) OR (set AND ablaze) OR landmine OR sabot! OR hostage! OR assassinat! OR shot OR murdered OR killed (Kriesi, Hanspeter et al. 2020: 14).

This search yielded an initial set of 5.2 million news reports published in the period from 2000 to 2015 of which only about five percent actually reported on protest events in the 30 countries of interest. Thus, making the following process necessary to reduce the large amount of false positives. The team proceeded as follows: (A) remove duplicated reports, (B) discard reports that do not cover relevant countries (using a meta-data filter), (C) apply a supervised document classifier in order to distinguish relevant reports from irrelevant ones, (D) discard textually similar reports, and (E) apply a supervised protest mention classifier (Kriesi, Hanspeter et al. 2020: 14-15).

During the manual coding procedure, which followed a simplified version of the PEA as developed by Kriesei et al (1995), the final identification of relevant documents took place (since the automated selection procedure was not able to eliminate all false positives) using a detailed list of unconventional or non-institutionalized political action forms (Kriesi, Hanspeter et al. 2020: 27-28, 31). These action forms include: demonstrations, violent protest, strikes, confrontations, blockades, petitions, symbolic actions, and other protests as well as a number of addressed issues and actors (Kriesi, Hanspeter et al. 2020: 9). For an

exhaustive list please refer to Kriesi, Hanspeter et al. 2020: 29. Afterwards, the research team coded the following overarching variables for each event: (a) the date of the event, (b) the location of the event, (c) the form of action, (d) the number of participants, (e) the issue of the protest, and lastly (f) the actors participating in or organizing the event (Kriesi, Hanspeter et al. 2020: 28).

In order to make the gathered data comparable across different countries, the research team employed various methods. Two of these methods are the use of separate sampling probabilities and the adjustment of the number of events (using a natural logarithmic scale) depending on whether a country is categorized as a small, medium-sized or large size. On top of that, another weight was added to control the bias resulting from the focus of the newswire agencies utilised to gather the data. If all the documents are taken from an agency focused on a specific country, they weigh less than those reports taken from general agencies to avoid over-reporting (Kriesi, Hanspeter et al. 2020: 32-33).

For an in depth look into the tuning of classification model thresholds please refer to Appendix A within the PolDem codebook. For an exhaustive explanation of the manual content analysis please refer to Appendix B within the PolDem codebook (Kriesi, Hanspeter et al. 2020: 54ff.).

Discuss Data relevant country coverage:

Country	Entries
Estonia	408
Latvia	582
Lithuania	665

Sources:

- (1) PolDem. Observatory for Political Conflict and Democracy in Europe. <https://poldem.eui.eu/>. Last accessed 30.09.2024.
- (2) Kriesi, Hanspeter et al. 2020. PolDem-Protest Dataset 30 European Countries, Version 1. https://poldem.eui.eu/downloads/pea/poldem-protest_30_codebook.pdf. Last accessed 30.09.2024.